

FULL TITLE OF THE STUDY

Use of antibiotics in ICU patients undergoing lavage-based diagnosis of pneumonia

SHORT STUDY TITLE / ACRONYM

Antibiotics after bronchoscopy

PROTOCOL VERSION NUMBER AND DATE

1.5 5/2/20

RESEARCH REFERENCE NUMBERS

Sponsor number: **A095506**

Sponsor	Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust (CUHNFT) Hills Road, Cambridge CB2 0QQ
Joint Sponsor	
Funder(s)	None
Collaborating Institutes	University of Cambridge
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ii. LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Define all unusual or 'technical' terms related to the study. Add or delete as appropriate to your study. Maintain alphabetical order for ease of reference.

CI	Chief Investigator
CUH	Cambridge University Hospitals
CUHNFT	Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust
EDSP	Electronic Data Security Policy
EHR	Electronic Health Records
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
HRA	Health Research Authority
NHS R&D	National Health Service Research & Development
PI	Principal Investigator
REC	Research Ethics Committee

iii. STUDY SUMMARY

Study Title	Use of antibiotics in ICU patients undergoing lavage-based diagnosis of pneumonia
Internal ref. no.	A095506
Study Design	Retrospective review of routinely collected data
Sample population	Mechanically ventilated patients in Intensive Care undergoing bronchoscopy for diagnosis of suspected pneumonia
Planned Sample Size	100 patients
Planned Study Period	Retrospective data collection for period January 2018-September 2019
Primary Objectives	Identify antibiotic use amongst patients undergoing lavage for diagnosis of pneumonia in intensive care to allow comparison with patients who entered the microarray study
Secondary Objectives	To describe the epidemiology of severe pneumonia in intensive care patients over the time of the recently completed microarray study.

iv. FUNDING

No funding, this study uses retrospective collation of routinely collected data and will be undertaken by NHS employees during their free time.

1 BACKGROUND

Pneumonia, a serious infection of the lungs, is a common reason for Intensive Care Unit (ICU) admission. It may also develop as a significant complication of being on a mechanical ventilator. Although the clinical diagnosis is generally straight-forward to make, determining which organism is causing the infection (pathogen) presents a much greater challenge. Existing detection of pathogens relies on growing the organism under specific conditions in a microbiology laboratory. This process is slow, typically taking 48 to 72 hours, and is influenced by factors such as presence of antibiotics and the ease with which specific organisms can be grown. Conventional microbiology may only be positive less than 40% of cases of pneumonia^{1, 2} and this means that patients are often treated with 'best guess' antibiotics. These antibiotics are generally broad spectrum, and risk the development of antibiotic resistance. Equally, organisms that are less commonly seen may not be covered by the initial antibiotic selection and may only be started once this organism is grown after 48 to 72 hours leading to delays in appropriate treatment. Our group has recently completed a study "The Taqman Microarray Card for Rapid Pathogen Identification in Ventilated Patients with Pneumonia" (short name "the microarray study") which evaluated the clinical performance and utility of a rapid molecular test for pneumonia. This current study will allow us to identify patients admitted during the study period who were not enrolled in the study due to lack of team availability to act as a comparator group to establish the impact of the microarray on antibiotic prescription.

2 RATIONALE:

We recently conducted an evaluation of a microarray-based test for respiratory pathogens in ventilated patients with pneumonia in Intensive Care. The study collected data regarding antibiotic prescription following the sampling of the lungs by washings (bronchoscopy and lavage), recruiting patients who were already undergoing this procedure for diagnostic purposes. During the study period there were times when the study team was not available due to working hours and holidays, and therefore there were a group of patients who underwent bronchoscopy and lavage for diagnosis of pneumonia but did not enter the microarray study. In order to establish the impact of the microarray on antibiotic prescription we intend to assess antibiotic use in patients who did not go into the study and compare this with patients who did.

3 OBJECTIVES, OUTCOME MEASURES/ENDPOINTS

3.1 Primary objectives

The primary objective is to establish the exposure of patients with severe pneumonia to antibiotics and compare this to patients who had diagnosis assisted by the microarray

3.2 Secondary objective

The secondary objective is to describe the epidemiology of severe pneumonia in intensive care during the period investigated.

3.3 Primary endpoint/outcome

Primary outcome is antibiotic use, measured in antibiotic days, in the seven days following lavage for diagnosis of pneumonia

3.4 Secondary endpoints/outcomes

Secondary outcomes are a description of the incidence of pneumonia undergoing bronchoscopic diagnosis and the clinical and demographic description of this population.

4 STUDY DESIGN

Retrospective cohort study using routinely collected clinical data

5 PATIENT INCLUSION CRITERIA

5.1 Inclusion criteria

- Male and female
- Age 18 or over
- Mechanically ventilated during the period 1/1/2018-31/09/2019
- Undergoing bronchoscopy and lavage for suspected pneumonia

5.2 Exclusion criteria

Participation in the microarray study

6 STATISTICS AND DATA ANALYSIS

Defined daily doses of antibiotics will be analysed using appropriate summary statistics, and will be compared to the summary statistic for antibiotic days and its converse, antibiotic free days, in patients who entered the microarray study. Appropriate comparisons, such as Mann-Whitney U test will be used to compare antibiotic exposure

Patient clinical and demographic features will be summarised by percentage (categorical variables) or by summary statistic (continuous variables) and compared with the microarray summary data by appropriate comparison tests (for example χ^2 or Fisher's exact test for categorical data, Mann-Whitney U test for summary of continuous data).

Data will all be aggregated before analysis and no individual patient data will be presented or leave Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust (CUHNFT) premises.

7 DATA PROTECTION AND MANAGEMENT

7.1 Legal Compliance

All investigators and study site staff will comply with the requirements the General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR) with regards to the collection, storage, processing and disclosure of personal information and will uphold the regulations' core principles. All data is de-identified before processing

7.2 Data extraction and anonymisation

The specific data extracted is listed in Appendix 1. Data will be pseudoanonymised by allocation of a unique study number. Deidentification is maintained by keeping the participant key, indicating the unique study numbers allocated, separate from the data on a password protected CUHNFT computer accessible only to members of the direct care team.

7.3 Data processing

All data will be pseudo-anonymised by a unique study number, with the code linking this to the patient record kept in a separate, password protected spreadsheet on a secure drive within CUH. Pseudoanonymised data will be collected on a password protected spreadsheet which will also be held on a secure drive within CUH. All analysis will be conducted on CUHNFT computers. Summary level data (population mean, median and spread) will be reported in reports produced for external consumption (peer reviewed literature, conference papers and project reports), but no individual patient level data will leave CUHNFT or be reported externally.

7.4 Long Term Data Storage

Pseudoanonymised data will be stored on a CUHNFT secure server for the duration of the study, and for 5 years after study findings are published in order to ensure that findings are verifiable.

8 ETHICAL AND REGULATORY CONSIDERATIONS

8.1 Ethical Approval

Internal R&D approval will be sought from CUH R&D in line with the guidance on collation and analysis of retrospective, routinely collected clinical data

8.3 Indemnity

The University of Cambridge provides insurance cover for both negligent and non-negligent harm for the design, management and relevant conduct of this study.

NHS indemnity applies to aspects of the study conducted by staff at CUHNFT.

8.4 Amendments

All amendments to the protocol will be discussed with the CUHNFT R&D department. Advice will be taken on the regulatory approvals required for the amendments, which may include HRA and REC review. Amendments submitted for regulatory review will not be implemented until the necessary regulatory approvals are received.

9 REFERENCES

1. Gadsby NJ, Russell CD, McHugh MP, et al. Comprehensive Molecular Testing for Respiratory Pathogens in Community-Acquired Pneumonia. *Clin Infect Dis*. January 2016:civ1214-civ1217. doi:10.1093/cid/civ1214.
2. Hellyer TP, Morris AC, Mcauley DF, et al. Diagnostic accuracy of pulmonary host inflammatory mediators in the exclusion of ventilator-acquired pneumonia. *Thorax*. 2015;70(1):41-47.

10. APPENDICIES

13.1 Appendix 1- Data fields

Information to be extracted is outlined in the table below, including how the information will be converted during the anonymisation process to ensure the collective data for each patient is not identifiable.

Information for extraction	Conversion of potentially sensitive information
Hospital number (patient identifier)	Anonymised unique patient study code
Sex	M/F
Date of birth	Converted to age at time of lavage to prevent identification of patient
Admission Diagnosis	Coded at high level to prevent identification of patients from diagnosis – see appendix 3 below for codes to be used
Antibiotic allergy	
Function Co-morbidity index	
Immunosuppression	Recorded as yes/no and category (drug, in-born error of immunity, acquired defect in immunity and haematological malignancy)
Pneumonia details	Hospital-acquired, ventilator-acquired or community-acquired
Microbiological results from culture and conventional PCR testing of lavage	
APACHE II score on admission	
Antibiotics commenced prior to lavage	
Oxygenation status before lavage	
White cell count and differential on day of lavage	
Antibiotics received in 7 and 28 days following lavage	
Mortality at 28 days	
Length of stay in ICU	
Duration of ventilation in ICU	

11. Appendix 2 – Amendment History

Amendment No.	Protocol version no.	Date issued	Author(s) of changes	Details of changes made

12. Appendix 3

Codes for admission diagnosis

1-Pneumonia, hospital acquired

2-pneumonia, community acquired

3-infection, non-pulmonary source

4-solid organ transplantation

5-pancreatitis

6-post-operative, emergency surgery

7-post-operative, elective surgery

8-Haematological malignancy

9- toxicological emergency (overdose)

10-cardiac arrest

11-neurological insult

12-major trauma

13-other